

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7921921>

**THE ROLE AND TASKS OF MINISTRIES IN THE STATE
ADMINISTRATION OF SOME ASIAN COUNTRIES**

Zokirov Shohruxbek Zohidjon ogli
Student of Kokand State Pedagogical
Institute
shohruxzokirov2320@gmail.com

Abstract: *The article contains scientific opinions about the role of ministries in the state administration of the developed countries of Asia and the Republic of Uzbekistan, their names, ongoing reforms, and the tasks of ministries.*

Key words: *Public administration, ministries, executive sponsorship, Asia, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, India, China, Saudi Arabia, Japan, tasks, reforms.*

Implementation of state power issue has been relevant at all times and still is. The institutional element of the state is state power organization, organization, i.e. formalized as an organization. The state as an organization is different can be interpreted from the point of view. In the deepest sense, the state is a hierarchical (step by step) that covers the entire population of the country. Organized) is an organization in which the population is the initial element of the state. This association of the population – in the organization, on the one hand – There are “managed citizens”, on the other side – the entire state organization control hardware is available. The organizational and material force that enables the state to exercise its power is the state apparatus (mechanism). This hardware (mechanism) means what the state is made of. The state apparatus is the state system of bodies exercising power. It is the goal of the state and performs basic functions aimed at performing tasks. Apparatus – Officials and management in the community is a sum of bodies. In the theory of state and law, the special organization that exercises state power is “state apparatus” and “state mechanism”. Expressed by terms.

The state mechanism is an integral hierarchical system of state bodies and institutions. Its integrity comes first with the unity of state power and its will, with the unity of principles, tasks and goals of state bodies and institutions is provided. State bodies, despite their differences, are one. Parts and are closely related to each other. For example, Parliament and the government has different powers, performs different tasks, but both of them jointly exercise a single state power, i.e. the activity of both is to create conditions for a decent life for citizens. They are interconnected and interconnected.

In many countries, the system of state power is based on the principles of the division of legislative, executive and judicial powers into three parts. Executive sponsorship is the main link of the state mechanism and works directly with the people. If we compare the state with a person, then executive patronage can be compared with a person’s heart. Since the heart produces blood and powers all the

Names of Ministries in Uzbekistan

1. Ministry of Economy	12. Ministry of Emergency Situations;
2. Ministry of Finance;	13. Ministry of Foreign Affairs;
3. Ministry of Agriculture;	14. Ministry of Justice;
4. Ministry of Water Economy;	15. Ministry of Foreign Trade;
5. Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations;	16. Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development;
6. Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education;	17. Ministry of housing and communal services;
7. Ministry of Public Education;	18. Ministry of Innovative Development;
8. Ministry of preschool education;	19. Ministry of physical education and sports;
9. Ministry of Health;	20. Ministry of Construction.
10. Ministry of Culture;	21. Ministry of Internal Affairs
11. Ministry of Defense;	

organs, the executive branch is also responsible for carrying out the tasks worked out by the state and issued by the legislature, and establishes control over them.

We all know that ministries, agencies, committees, organizations, committees, local governments, etc. Are the backbone of executive power. In this article we want to talk about the ministries, which are

one of the branches of the executive branch. At the same time, there are studies on the activities of ministries in the developed countries of Asia, the tasks assigned to them and the achievements and reforms achieved due to this. A ministry is an executive body that oversees a particular sector in certain countries. The head of the ministry is usually a government official. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry is the central governing body of the state, an important part of the state court. "Its main task is to lead a certain branch of the economy, socio-cultural construction and administrative-political activities, to ensure the development of the assigned branch in all aspects. Ministries work under the leadership of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and resolve all issues related to the network within their jurisdiction. The ministry is headed by a minister who is part of the government. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan appoints and dismisses members of the Cabinet of Ministers, and then submits these issues to the Supreme Council for approval." ("O'zbekiston Respublikasining Konstitutsiyasi", 93-modda).

Today, one of the main directions of administrative reforms in Uzbekistan is implementation to increase the efficiency of the authorities, their role and responsibility in this regard consists of strengthening. The executive bodies of the local government are each of the state is a part of the activity of a region. This authority has a wide range of powers, including most civil servants of government agencies. The rule of law according to the concept, to carry out activities related to the rights and interests of citizens enforcement of local laws on territories that objectively require an increase is the main task of executive authorities. "The proposal of the Council of the Agency for Strategic Reforms under the President to reduce the number of independent executive authorities of the republic from 61 to 28, including the number of ministries from 25 to 21, as part of the first stage of the administrative reforms of New Uzbekistan, starting from January 1, 2023. 'enslaved. In particular, the ministries of economy and finance, pre-school education and public

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION

education, construction and housing and communal services, higher education and innovation, as well as the ministries of culture and tourism were merged.”¹

India is a country with a large economy in Asia and the world. The labor force in the country is considered sufficient. It is among the developed G20 countries of the

Names of Ministries in India

1. Ministry of Information and Broadcasting	27. Ministry of Coal
2. Ministry of Agriculture	28. Ministry of Personnel, Public Grievances & Pensions
3. Ministry of Textiles	29. Ministry of Law & Justice
4. Ministry of Commerce & Industry	30. Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs
5. Ministry of Defence	31. Ministry of Science & Technology
6. Ministry of Finance	32. Ministry of Culture
7. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	33. Ministry of Steel
8. Ministry of Home Affairs	34. Ministry of Labour & Employment
9. Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs	35. Ministry of Communications
10. Ministry of Education	36. Ministry of Civil Aviation
11. Ministry of Panchayati Raj	37. Ministry of New and Renewable Energy
12. Ministry of Petroleum & Natural Gas	38. Ministry of Tourism
13. Ministry of Power	39. Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food & Public Distribution
14. Ministry of Railways	40. Ministry of Food Processing Industries
15. Ministry of Road Transport & Highways	41. Ministry of chemicals and fertilizers
16. Ministry of Rural Development	42. Ministry of Mines
17. Ministry of Urban Development	43. Ministry of Shipping
18. Ministry of Water Resources	44. Ministry of Disinvestment
19. Ministry of Women & Child Development	45. Ministry of Tribal Affairs
20. Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports	46. Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment
21. Ministry of Minority Affairs	47. Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises
22. Ministry of Corporate Affairs	48. Ministry of Heavy Industries & Public Enterprises
23. Ministry of Earth Science	49. Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation
24. Ministry of Drinking Water & Sanitation	
25. Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship	
26. Ministry of Development of North-East Region	

world. In India, too, reforms of the executive branch are constantly being implemented. The ministerial system of executive patronage is no exception! As everyone knows, India is one of the most populous countries in the world. There is a large population, and in order to realize their needs and wishes, the executive power should have a large number of educated employees, as

well as a high level of knowledge. And this system is well established and there are 49 ministries alone in India apart from agencies, committees and others.

The government of China is structured in a unique way, with a focus on centralized power and control. The many ministries that make up the government play a crucial role in managing the vast array of responsibilities that come with running a country of over a billion people. In this paper, we will explore the functions and responsibilities of the ministries in the Chinese government, specifically looking at the roles of the various ministries in relation to each other and the country as a whole.

Names of Ministries in PR China

1. Ministry of Foreign Affairs	12. Ministry of Railways
2. Ministry of National Defense	13. Ministry of Communications
3. Ministry of Education	14. Ministry of Information Industry
4. Ministry of Science and Technology	15. Ministry of Water Resources
5. Ministry of Public Security	16. Ministry of Agriculture
6. Ministry of State Security	17. Minister of Commerce Ministry of Culture
7. Ministry of Supervision	18. Ministry of Health
8. Ministry of Land and Resources	19. Ministry of Civil Affairs
9. Ministry of Construction	20. Ministry of Justice
10. Ministry of Labor and Social Security	21. Ministry of Finances
11. Ministry of Personnel	

The Chinese government's ministries have significant responsibilities in managing the country's vast and complex systems. Each ministry plays a crucial role in maintaining order, managing finances, promoting development, and ensuring national security. This paper has provided an overview of the functions and responsibilities of some of the key ministries in China's government. Further research

responsibilities of some of the key ministries in China's government. Further research

¹ “O‘zbekistonda vazirliklar soni qisqartirilmoqda. Moliya va iqtisodiyot vazirliklari qo‘shildi”

<https://kun.uz/uz/news/2022/12/24/prezident-farmoni-bilan-vazirliklar-soni-qisqartirilmoqda-moliya-va-iqtisodiyot-vazirliklari-qoshildi>

and analysis into these ministries' roles and responsibilities can contribute to a better understanding of the Chinese government's structure and management.

Kazakhstan has also been implementing many reforms in ministries in recent years. The country located in the center of Asia is a neighbor of our country. One of the

Names of Ministries in Kazakhstan

1. Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Kazakhstan	12. Ministry of Industry and Infrastructural Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan
2. Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Kazakhstan	13. Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan
3. Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Kazakhstan	14. Ministry of Culture and Sport of the Republic of Kazakhstan
4. Ministry of Information and Social Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan	15. Ministry of National Economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan
5. Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Kazakhstan	16. Ministry of Digital Development, Innovations and Aerospace Industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan
6. Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Kazakhstan	17. Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Kazakhstan
7. Ministry of Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan	18. Ministry of Trade and Integration of the Republic of Kazakhstan
8. Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan	19. Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Kazakhstan
9. Ministry of Healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan	
10. Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of Population of the Republic of Kazakhstan	
11. Ministry for Emergency Situations of the Republic of Kazakhstan	

closest strategic and economic partners of Uzbekistan. Of course, the political changes in the neighboring country do not leave us indifferent. The last changes in the ministries were carried out in October 2022 based on the decree of the President of Kazakhstan. Today there are 19 ministries in Kazakhstan, you can get acquainted with them in the table above.

Saudi Arabia is a country located in the Middle East, with a government structure that is a monarchy. The government of Saudi Arabia is divided into various ministries that oversee different areas related to the well-being and development of the country. Each ministry has its role and responsibilities that contribute to the overall development of the country. This article seeks to explore the responsibilities of Saudi Arabian government ministries and how they contribute to the country's development.

Names of Ministries in Saudia Arabia

1. Deputy Prime Minister	14. Minister of Islamic Affairs, Call and Guidance
2. Minister of the National Guard	15. Minister of Justice
3. Minister of Interior	16. Minister of Labor and Social Development
4. Minister of Education	17. Minister of Energy, Industry and Mineral Resources
5. Minister of Municipal and Rural Affairs	18. Minister of Hajj and Umrah
6. Minister of Foreign Affairs	19. Minister of National Economy and Planning
7. Minister of Environment, Water and Agriculture	20. Minister of Communications and Information Technology
8. Minister of Civil Service	21. Minister of Transport
9. Minister of Finance	22. Ministers of State
10. Minister of Health	
11. Minister of Commerce and Investment	
12. Minister of Culture and Information	
13. Minister of Housing	

The Saudi Arabian government's ministries play a crucial role in the country's development. They carry out their tasks and responsibilities diligently and contribute to the well-being of the people of Saudi Arabia. Their efforts have led to significant developments, including economic growth, infrastructure development, and social progress, among others. A better

understanding of the responsibilities of these ministries is essential in determining the success and effectiveness of the Saudi Arabian government.

Japan is one of the most developed countries in Asia and is located in the east of Asia. Japan is rapidly developing due to the orderly society, paying serious attention to every field. Ministries and agencies form the basis of executive power in the

country. Many tasks are assigned to ministries and agencies. However, it is no secret that the main task is carried out by the ministries.

The Cabinet has the Cabinet Office and 11 Ministries, which are established by the respective Establishment Laws and are enumerated in the National Government Organization Law, as well as the Cabinet Secretariat, Cabinet Legislation Bureau, National Personnel Authority, Security Council of Japan, and other Cabinet organs. There is the Board of Audit which is a constitutionally independent organization to audit the final accounts of the State and other public corporations

Names of Ministries in Japan

1. Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications	7. Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries
2. Ministry of Justice	8. Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry
3. Ministry of Foreign Affairs	9. Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism
4. Ministry of Finance	10. Ministry of the Environment
5. Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology	11. Ministry of Defense
6. Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare	

and agencies.

We see that different tasks are assigned to the ministries in each country. But the only goal is to serve the people. In our opinion, expanding the list of ministries is ineffective rather than constantly changing it. This can be seen in the case of Japan. As many as 11 ministries in the whole country are moving towards development by performing large-scale tasks. In the article, information and tables on the ministries of the countries mentioned above were given.

References:

1. O‘zbekistan Respublikasining Konstitutsiyasi
2. O‘zbekiston Yuridik ensiklopediyasi
3. “Davlat va huquq nazariyasi”. Odilqoriyev X.T. Toshkent-2018.
4. Usmonova, O. (2023). O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT HOKIMIYATINI AMALGA OSHIRISH SHAKLLARI. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(2 Part 2), 28-30.
5. Zohidjon o‘g‘li, Z. S. (2023). Attitude to the law in Japan Similarities in the constitutions of Uzbekistan and Japan. *Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 16, 16-18.
6. “O‘zbekistonda vazirliklar soni qisqartirilmoqda. Moliya va iqtisodiyot vazirliklari qo‘shildi” <https://kun.uz/uz/news/2022/12/24/prezident-farmoni-bilan-vazirliklar-soni-qisqartirilmoqda-moliya-va-iqtisodiyot-vazirliklari-qoshildi>
7. “Integrated Government Online Directory : Union Government : Ministries” <https://igod.gov.in/ug/E002/organizations>
8. https://egov.kz/cms/en/information/state_agencies/ministries_committees
9. “List of ministries, commissions of China’s cabinet after reform - Xinhua | English.news.cn” http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/2018-03/18/c_137046383.htm

10. “Ministries | The Embassy of The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia”
<https://www.saudiembassy.net/ministries>
11. “Central Government Ministries and Agencies - Tokyo Metropolitan Government”
<https://www.metro.tokyo.lg.jp/english/directory/ministries.html>